

Ultra-thin Infrared Optical Gain Medium and Optically-pumped Stimulated Emission in PbS Colloidal Quantum Dot LEDs

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Colloidal semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) can be considered as a promising material platform for use in solution-processed laser diodes. However, due to some fundamental challenges, the realization of electrically pumped lasing based on QDs remains unresolved. Here, we employ a binary blend of QDs and ZnO nanocrystals, which serve as nano-sized scatterers to facilitate waveguide gain in ultra-thin films. By carefully engineering the electric field in these films, we observed infrared amplified spontaneous emission in a record thin colloidal gain medium, with a thickness of 16 nm, at a wavelength of 1675 nm. Employing these binary blends as a gain medium, we demonstrate optically pumped infrared stimulated emission in a full-stacked light emitting diode (LED) device. Our functional LED device, which comprises of a single layer of graphene as anode electrode, shows strong electroluminescence under electrical injection. This study suggests a promising device for realizing infrared QD based laser diodes.

1. Introduction

Short-wave infrared lasers have a broad range of applications, including fiber optic telecommunication,^[1,2] CMOS photonics,^[3,4] and eye-safe LIDAR applications.^[5,6] The existing technologies for short-wave infrared lasers are based on epitaxially grown III-V semiconductors^[7-9] and Erbium-doped optical fibers.^[10,11] The aforementioned technologies can neither be integrated into silicon technology nor do they cover the full optical telecommunication window. Colloidal semiconductor quantum dots (QDs) emerged as an alternative and promising gain medium thanks to their favorable optical and electrical properties, including spectral tunability,^[12,13] compatibility with diverse matrices,^[14,15] and high photoluminescence quantum efficiency.^[13,16] Most recently, tunable room-temperature, near-infrared stimulated emission and lasing have been successfully demonstrated using PbS QDs as a gain medium.^[17-19] However, stimulated emission under electrical or continuous-wave pumping using PbS-based QDs has yet to be demonstrated. Due to the multiexcitonic nature of light amplification in PbS, it is essential to suppress undesired non-radiative Auger recombination, whereby the energy of an exciton recombination is delivered to a third carrier.^[20] In order to eventually realize electrically-driven infrared stimulated emission and lasing in QDs, the following challenges should be addressed: 1) to demonstrate optical gain in a full-LED device stack, including conductive layers and contacts, 2) to obtain net gain and stimulated emission in ultrathin film gain medium in order to facilitate efficient electrical injection and 3) to increase the robustness of the device upon high current density needed to achieve population inversion.^[21,22]

In the present study, we address the first two challenges and demonstrate a functional infrared EL device in an all colloidal light emitting diode (LED) device, which exhibits stimulated emission characteristics under optical pumping. In previous studies we have demonstrated that by blending ZnO nanocrystals (NCs) with PbS QDs the electronic properties of the gain material can be improved to achieve low-threshold ASE.^[17] Herein, we demonstrate an EL device architecture with a PbS/ZnO blend acting as the thin film active media of an LED device. Additional to improving ASE performance, the ZnO NCs are also observed to form nanoclusters which act as scattering sites that facilitate ASE propagation below the waveguide cut-off thickness. By carefully adjusting the loading amount of ZnO in PbS/ZnO blend, we are able to attain stimulated emission at record a subwavelength gain medium thickness of 16 nm (i.e. $\lambda/100$). Importantly, stimulated emission is also realized in a complete LED device structure including an anode electrode that is made of a single-layer of graphene. It is noteworthy that although lasing action has been previously shown in LED-like structure in the visible,^[22] none of those devices included the anode electrode which is crucial for a real EL

device, and the lasing emission was observed to disappear in the vicinity of a conventional metal electrode, due to optical losses.^[22]

2. Results & Discussion

The standard architecture for demonstrating amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) in thin film is a slab waveguide where the stimulated emission is confined in a high refractive index gain medium. A homogenous thin film asymmetric waveguide has a minimum thickness for which it can still support a guiding mode for a given wavelength. We posited that the presence of low refractive index ZnO NCs blended with PbS QDs active medium at the nanoscale would allow us to overcome this critical thickness threshold by assisted scattering. **Figure 1a** illustrates the configuration for ASE measurements of the thin films, showing how spontaneous emission is propagated in-plane, and then amplified along the pump stripe. The resultant ASE signal is then collected at the edge of the film, perpendicular to the excitation beam. Using our proposed architecture, we would be able to achieve ASE in the thicknesses that are required for high current injection in LED structures. Using scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM)-EDS elemental mapping, shown in **Figure 1b** superposed on a dark field image, the ratio of Pb to Zn was measured to be 68:32%. From TEM images, we extracted the diameter of PbS QDs and ZnO NCs as ~ 5.8 nm and 6 nm respectively, and as shown in **Figure 1b**, ZnO NCs tended to form nano-clusters. We employed atomic force microscopy (AFM) to assess the thickness and surface morphology of our samples, the results of which are illustrated in **Figure 1c&d**, where the thickness of the film is measured to be ~ 16 nm with a r.m.s. value of 0.86 nm. The AFM images of thin films with different thickness are shown in Supplementary **Figure S1&S2**. Furthermore, the scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of bare-PbS and PbS/ZnO blends are displayed in **Figure 1e** and **Figure 1f**, respectively. As can be seen, introducing ZnO NCs improved the uniformity of the thin film formation which can be attributed to better nucleation of PbS QDs during the spin-coating process.^[23] This results in a smooth thin film gain medium with the PbS/ZnO blend, in which the surface coverage reaches near unity for a single layer deposition, with no noticeable cracks or voids.

To investigate the optical gain performance of our devices, we spin-coated the PbS/ZnO blend, with a ratio of 7:3, on a glass substrate. We controlled the thickness of the samples via repeated spin-coating and ligand exchange procedures (see Methods). ASE spectra from a sample as thin as ~ 16 nm ($< \frac{\lambda}{100}$) are plotted in **Figure 2a** as a function of pump fluence. **Figure 2b** depicts the integrated intensity of the ASE spectra against pump fluence along with the corresponding the full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of each spectrum. The photoluminescence (PL)

intensity increases linearly with pump intensity at low fluences and then exhibits a super-linear behavior above the threshold of 2.9 mJ.cm^{-2} , a clear signature of light amplification. Above the ASE threshold, the FWHM of the spectra drastically drops from $\sim 125 \text{ nm}$ to $\sim 17 \text{ nm}$. To the best of our knowledge, this is the thinnest attained thickness for ASE using a colloidal gain medium with a thickness of $\sim 16 \text{ nm}$, with an ASE peak wavelength of $\sim 1675 \text{ nm}$. Note that 16 nm is below the theoretical waveguide cut-off thickness of a homogenous medium at this wavelength (56 nm).

As discussed above, for electrically pumped QD lasers, it is essential to achieve optical gain in ultra-thin films in order to facilitate charge injection into the active medium for achieving population inversion;^[21,22] as thin active media result in a balanced carrier supply to the QDs.^[16] Furthermore, as shown in **Figure 2c**, by increasing the thickness of the PbS/ZnO films, the ASE peak is gradually blue-shifted. For instance, the ASE peak for a 70-nm thick film appears at $\sim 1604 \text{ nm}$. This blue-shifting of the ASE peak can be attributed to the increased scattering in thicker films. The ASE thresholds for films with varying thicknesses are summarized in **Figure 2d**, decreasing from 2.9 mJ.cm^{-2} to 0.5 mJ.cm^{-2} having a film thicknesses of 16 nm and 140 nm respectively. We measured net optical gain (G) and waveguide loss coefficients (α) for bare-PbS and PbS/ZnO blend with varying thickness via the variable stripe length (VSL) and moving-edge loss methods (see Supplementary Note 1). These results are depicted in Supplementary **Figure S3&S4**. At similar pump fluences, G is lower in the PbS/ZnO blend compared to bare-PbS films due to the reduced amount of gain material the blend. Similarly, thanks to the reduction of re-absorption losses in blends, α dropped to 9 cm^{-1} in PbS/ZnO blend sample within a thickness of $\sim 25 \text{ nm}$, while it is 23 cm^{-1} for bare-PbS samples having a thickness of $\sim 110 \text{ nm}$. (see Supplementary **Figure S5**).

To gain further insights into our experimental ASE observation of the QD ultra-thin films, we employed a full-field electromagnetic numerical model. In principle, our structure can be modelled as an asymmetric slab waveguide, in which the gain medium is sandwiched between semi-infinite fused silica and air layers. **Figure 3a,b** depict the asymmetric planar waveguide enabling electromagnetic modes to propagate along the waveguide, while fundamental transverse electric field (TE) and transverse magnetic field (TM) modes requires a minimum thickness to be confined inside the active region. The critical thicknesses for TE and TM can be calculated from the following expressions:^[24]

$$t_{TE} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{n_2^2 - n_3^2}} \left[m\pi + \arctan\left(\sqrt{\frac{n_3^2 - n_1^2}{n_2^2 - n_3^2}}\right) \right] \quad (\text{Equation. 1})$$

$$t_{TM} = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi\sqrt{n_2^2 - n_3^2}} \left[m\pi + \arctan \left(\frac{n_2^2}{n_1^2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{n_3^2 - n_1^2}{n_2^2 - n_3^2}} \right) \right) \right]$$

Using Equation 1, the waveguide cut-off thickness is plotted against wavelength in **Figure 3c** for the fundamental TE and TM modes ($m=0$). For $\lambda = 1675$ nm, the minimum thicknesses for propagation of TE₀ and TM₀ in PbS solid film are 56 and 158 nm, respectively. While, for PbS/ZnO blends, t_{TE_0} and t_{TM_0} are 106 and 220 nm. Note, we extracted the refractive indices of films using spectroscopic ellipsometry (see Supplementary **Figure S7**). In PbS/ZnO blends, the onset experimental thickness for observing ASE signal in thin film configuration is ~ 16 nm. Therefore, the mode confinement in our architecture does not obey the rules of a conventional slab waveguide. We modelled our thin film devices using an FDTD solver (see Method section). In the case of bare-PbS, the thin film of QDs is approximated as a homogenous medium, while for PbS/ZnO blend, the ZnO NCs are located inside the homogenous medium of PbS thin film as shown in **Figure 3b**. Note, the loading of ZnO NCs is 30% of the whole volume, which was extracted from STEM-EDS mapping images (see **Figure 1b**). In our model, the semi-infinite SiO₂ substrate extends from $z = -\infty$ to $z = 0$, the active medium spreads from $z = 0$ to $z = 16$ nm, and above the structure is air. **Figure 3d** plots the electric field (E-field) intensity distribution in z-direction ($|E_z|^2$) along the lateral direction of the sample at different z positions within a bare-PbS film, where the majority of E-field propagates in the substrate and air. However, in the PbS/ZnO blended thin film, the E-field is enhanced at the position of ZnO nano-clusters owing to the strong scattering of light as can be seen in **Figure 3e** (dark blue line, $z = 8$ nm which is the middle of the gain medium). Although, similar behavior is also observed at the interfaces, the intensity of scattering is significantly larger at the center of the gain medium ($z = 8$ nm). At approximately one wavelength distance from the source injection, the E-field intensity is integrated over the xy-plane at corresponding heights (z's). Another notable observation is the emergence of a propagation mode in PbS/ZnO blend sample, where the E-field intensity exhibits a maximum in the gain medium, while there is no variation of E-field intensity in the bare-PbS case as depicted in **Figure 3f**. **Figure 3g** displays the E-field distribution over the xy-plane (in the middle of gain medium, $z = 8$ nm) and xz-plane for bare-PbS thin film, where there is no abrupt change in the E-field intensity. However, as shown in **Figure 3h**, the E-field intensity is significantly enhanced at the surface of ZnO NCs where due to the cluster formation of ZnO NCs, the electromagnetic wave propagates between these nano-clusters. It is worth mentioning that the scattering from ZnO nano-clusters allowed us to observe random lasing behavior in our thin film device with a thickness of 68 ± 6 nm on a glass substrate, which is plotted in Supplementary **Figure S6**, showing a narrow lasing mode, that outcompetes

other modes, within a linewidth of 4 nm (1.86 meV) at ~1630 nm, and exhibits a lasing threshold of 4.60 mJ cm⁻².

Finally, we fabricated a complete LED device stack comprising of engineered indium tin oxide (E-ITO) as a cathode electrode, a layer of ZnO NCs acting as electron transport layer (ETL), the PbS/ZnO blend as active medium (0.8 eV bandgap PbS QDs), a hole transport layer (HTL) made from large-bandgap PbS QDs (1.77 eV), and single-layer of graphene serving as the anode electrode. We engineered the optical constant of as-deposited ITO, to achieve a transmission of above 85% across our operating wavelength window (see Supplementary **Figure S8**), allowing us to observe stimulated emission on E-ITO substrates. Un-engineered ITO, in contrast, has transmission values down to as low as 60%, adding to much optical loss for an ASE signal to propagate along the sample. Note, the thickness of the ETL, gain medium and HTL are around 40 nm, 80 nm and 20 nm, respectively. **Figure 4a** is a schematic illustration of the tested LED structure exhibiting electrically injected infrared SE, as well as showing infrared ASE under optical laser excitation. The bias dependent LED device exhibits infrared SE at a wavelength of 1563 nm as shown in **Figure 4b**. Moreover, the infrared images of the LED device taken from the surface of the structure are depicted in **Figure 4c**. At 2 V the LED is in the off-state, while it at 5 V it is in the on-state. By applying sufficient bias to the electrodes, bright infrared emission is clearly visible from the graphene covered portion of the device. By pumping our LED device under stripe excitation of a femto-second laser (fs-laser), we observed an infrared stimulated emission peak at ~1607 nm as depicted in **Figure 4d**. The corresponding integrated intensity of ASE spectra versus excitation fluence is shown in **Figure 4e** for both with and without top electrode (i.e., graphene layer). The ASE threshold for the case of without graphene is ~820 μJ.cm⁻² which then increases slightly to 840 μJ.cm⁻² when the graphene was placed on top. This can be attributed to the graphene transfer procedure (see Methods section). It is worth mentioning that our proposed PbS/ZnO blend even allows us to achieve net optical gain in a full LED stack device.

3. Conclusion

In conclusion, we report near-infrared stimulated emission in a record thin colloidal gain medium. Our novel PbS/ZnO blends strongly interact with photons due to nano-cluster scatterers, resulting in propagation of generated stimulated emission along the surface of the

devices below the fundamental cut-off thickness for an asymmetric slab waveguide. Moreover, we show ASE in full-stack LED structure made of QDs as the gain medium under optical excitation. In our LED device, we employed a single-layer of graphene as an anode electrode instead of the conventional metals which results in quenching of ASE mode in the gain media. Our results will pave the way to realize a true electrically-driven laser made of QDs as the gain medium.

4. Experimental section

PbS QDs synthesis. 0.8 eV excitonic peak PbS QDs were synthesized under inert atmosphere by hot injection method. Briefly, 0.446 g PbO, 50 mL 1-octadecene (ODE) and 3.8 mL oleic acid were heated at 100°C under vacuum for 1h to form the lead precursor (lead oleate). Once under argon, a solution of 65 μ L hexamethyldisilathiane (HMS) in 3 mL ODE was quickly injected. After 6 minutes of reaction, a second solution of 75 μ L HMS in 9 mL ODE was injected dropwise. Subsequently, the solution was cooled down naturally to room temperature. PbS QDs were precipitated with the addition of a mixture of acetone/ethanol and re-dispersed in anhydrous toluene. This purification process was repeated two more times. Finally, the concentration of PbS QDs was adjusted to 30 mg/mL. The last step of purification and the adjustment of the concentration were done inside the glovebox in order to avoid oxidation.

1.77 eV excitonic peak PbS QDs were synthesized following the standard recipe. 0.446 g PbO, 18 mL ODE and 1.6 mL oleic acid were degassed for 1h under vacuum at 100°C. Once under argon, the temperature was set at 80°C and 210 μ L HMS in 5 mL ODE was quickly injected. After 25 seconds the reaction was quenched with cold acetone and QDs were collected by precipitation. The PbS QDs were purified by dispersion/precipitation with anhydrous toluene/acetone three times. Finally, the concentration was adjusted to 30 mg/mL and the sample was stored at low temperature to avoid Ostwald ripening.

ZnO NCs synthesis: ZnO NCs were synthesized based on the method shown previously.^[25] Briefly, 2.95 g of Zinc acetate dihydrate was dissolved in 125 mL of methanol under continuous stirring, while the temperature of the heater was set at 60°C. Separately, 1.48 g of KOH was dissolved in 65 mL of methanol. When the temperature of Zinc acetate dihydrate solution reached to \sim 60°C, the solution of KOH was slowly added to it in roughly 4 minutes, and the reaction was left for 2.5 hours. After finishing the reaction, the heater was removed, and the solution was slowly cooled down to room temperature under continuous stirring. Then, the synthesized ZnO NCs solution was centrifuged at 3500 r.p.m. for 5 min. The supernatant was removed and the remaining NCs were dispersed in methanol, the centrifuge step was repeated

three times. Finally, the ZnO NCs were dispersed in a solution of 5% (v/v) butylamine in toluene for making the binary blend solutions, and in 2% (v/v) butylamine in chloroform for formation of the electron transport layer.

Active layer deposition: The active layer was deposited on the desired substrate using spin coating method. First, 50 μL of QDs solution was poured on the pre-cleaned substrate, spin coating started after 5 s, with a spin speed of 2500 r.p.m. for 15 s. The then formed surface of PbS QDs was covered with a prepared inorganic ligand solution of ZnI_2/MPA (mixing of 8 mg/ml zinc iodide (ZnI_2) in methanol and 0.015% (v/v) 3-mercaptopropionic acid (MPA) in methanol). After 7 seconds of ligand exchange time, the spin coating was restarted at a spin speed of 2500 r.p.m. for 40 s. During this time the excess organics ligands were cleaned with a few drops of methanol. The above-mentioned steps were repeated until reaching the desired thickness. Before mixing, the ZnO NCs were prepared in separate vials with the same concentration as PbS QDs. For the PbS/ZnO binary blend solution, the PbS QDs solution was mixed with the ZnO solution at 30% loading content. The film thicknesses were measured via an AFM and a profilometer.

ASE characterization: The devices were optically pumped by a femtosecond Yt:YAG ORAGAMI laser (NKT Photonics) operating at 1030 nm within a pulse width of 300 fs at a repetition rate of 10 kHz. The excitation fluence was adjusted using a variable neutral density. The laser beam was focused as a stripe excitation on the sample using a cylindrical lens with a focal length of 20 cm. Using a lens with a focal length of 50 mm and diameter of 2 inches, the ASE spectra were collected perpendicular to the excitation beam. Utilizing free-space optics, the collected ASE signal was coupled into Kymera 328i spectrograph (Oxford Instruments. Andor) equipped with a InGaAs camera through a 100 μm slit via a lens with $f = 20$ cm.

Lumerical FDTD simulation: Commercial software, Ansys Lumerical Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD), is used for full electromagnetic simulations. Thin (16 nm) PbS layer is placed on top of a semi-infinite SiO_2 substrate ($z \leq 0$). Clusters of spherical ZnO particles are randomly distributed inside the PbS layer. The fundamental mode is calculated and injected towards x direction by the built-in mode source. The fields are recorded by frequency-domain field and power monitors. Perfectly matched layers (PML) boundary conditions are used at $\pm x$ and $\pm z$ boundaries, and periodic boundary conditions are used at $\pm y$ boundaries.

Engineered-indium tin oxide (E-ITO)-coated glass substrate preparation: The E-ITO is made by a low temperature annealing (LTA) of as-deposited ITO based on the method explained in our previous work.^[26] ITO films of 100 nm were deposited by the University of Stuttgart on

fused silica substrates via sputtering at room temperature. In the LTA process, the as-deposited ITO is annealed on a hotplate at 350 °C for 3 hours, in the ambient atmosphere.

Graphene layer transfer: CVD-grown monolayer graphene on copper with polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) on top (purchased from Graphenea S.A) was cut to match the sample dimensions. The copper was etched in an ammonium persulfate solution in deionized water (3 g/ml) for 3 hours. The remaining PMMA/graphene sheet is further cleaned in deionized water and transferred onto the sample. The sample with the graphene/PMMA layer is dried overnight in vacuum. PMMA is removed with acetone and isopropanol to obtain the graphene layer on top of our devices.

LED device fabrication: The LED device was fabricated on a pre-cleaned E-ITO substrate. The electron transport layer was made of ZnO NCs by spin casting ZnO NCs in chloroform at a spin speed of 4000 r.p.m. for 60 s. The active medium was spun on top of the ZnO layer as described in the active layer deposition section. The hole transport layer was formed using PbS QDs of smaller diameter which was treated by a solution of 0.02% ethanedithiol in acetonitrile. The graphene layer was transferred in a way mentioned above. To prevent from scratching the graphene layer, we deposited approximately 50 nm Au through a pre-patterned mask in thermal evaporator (Nano 36 Kurt J. Lesker).

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Author contribution

G.K. co-conceived the idea and supervised the study at all stages. N.T. co-conceived the concept and fabricated, characterized the laser and LED devices, and analyzed data. N.T. and G.K. designed the experiments. I.T., N.T., and K.A. performed FDTD simulations. M.D. synthesized PbS QDs. G.L.W. contributed to discussions and ASE measurements. V.P. developed and G.C. provided E-ITO-coated glass substrates. A.S. carried out TEM imaging. N.T. conducted SEM characterizations. N.T. and O.Ö. conducted graphene layer transfer. B.K. performed AFM measurements. N.T. and G.K. wrote the manuscript with contributions from all authors.

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Figure 1. Characterization of bare-PbS and PbS/ZnO blend samples. **a**, Schematic illustration of ASE measurement. **b**, STEM-EDS elemental mapping PbS/ZnO blend, where Pb:ZnO is 68:32%. **c**, AFM image showing morphology of PbS/ZnO blend thin film having a thickness of 16 nm. **d**, height profile of PbS/ZnO blend thin film. SEM image of a single layer of **(e)** bare-PbS and **(f)** PbS/ZnO blend on silicon substrate. Inset shows the zoom in image of the indicated region.

Figure 2. ASE characterization of PbS/ZnO blend sample. **a**, ASE spectra from a blend of PbS/ZnO (30%), having a thickness of 16 nm, as function of fluence. **b**, Normalized integrated intensity of the spectra as a function of pump fluence, with corresponding FWHM. **c**, Emission spectra of PbS/ZnO (30%) blend sample with different thicknesses of 16, 25, 45 and 70 nm. **d**, Evolution of ASE threshold with increasing thickness of thin films.

Figure 3. Full numerical electromagnetic model. **a,b**, Schematic drawing of an asymmetric slab-waveguide made of bare-PbS **(a)** and a PbS/ZnO blend **(b)**. **c**, Calculated gain medium cut-off thickness for supporting fundamental TE and TM in bare-PbS **(top panel)** and PbS/ZnO blend **(bottom panel)** devices as a function of wavelength. **d,e**, Electric field intensity ($|E|^2$) variation along the lateral side of samples at different heights for bare-PbS **(d)** and PbS/ZnO blend **(e)**. **f**, Electric field intensity ($|E|^2$) variation along vertical direction of the samples for bare-PbS and PbS/ZnO blend. Note, the thin film extends from 0 to 16 nm. **g,h**, Electric field distribution along xy-plane and xz-plane for bare-PbS **(g)** and PbS/ZnO **(h)**. Note, all E-fields are recorded at ASE wavelength of 1675 nm.

Figure 4. A full-LED device stack as both optically-pumped infrared-ASE and electrically-driven infrared-SE device. **a**, Schematic illustration of a complete LED structure. **b**, SE spectra of electrically excited LED as a function of bias voltages. **c**, Infrared images taken from the surface of the LED structure under 2 V and 5 V where LED is -off and -on, correspondingly, with the graphene layer indicated. **d**, ASE spectra as a function of excitation fluence under femto-second laser pumping in full-LED device, where the anode layer is made of a single layer of graphene. **e**, Normalized integrated intensity of ASE spectra against pump fluence for the devices with and without anode electrode.